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Name: Aleksejs Vesjolijs

Organisation: Transport and Telecommunication Institute

E-Mail address: Vesjolijs.A@tsi.lv

STATE-OF-THE-ART ON HYPERLOOP TECHNOLOGY

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INTRODUCTION

Imagine food supplies delivered from Lisbon to Stockholm in 180 minutes, German factory parts moving to Helsinki in 80 minutes, while Istanbul - Madrid transfer will take less than lecture time at university. Hyperloop (HL) is a break-through technology for super-fast-speed land transportation introduced in 2013, envisioned by Tesla and Space X (Tesla, 2023). Hyperloop visionary leader Elon Musk promises faster, safer, cheaper, more accessible, weather-resilient, reliant self-powering, impenetrable by earthquakes and not disruptive technology compared to the alternatives. Pneumatic-trains concept proposes solution for the specific case of city pairs that are less than about 1500 km apart. The goal of the Hyperloop is to provide a faster, more efficient, and more sustainable mode of transportation that can reduce travel times and connect cities and regions more effectively (Tesla, 2023).

Hyperloop has been declared as an industry-changing technology by the European Commission in its European Union Sustainable (ERA, 2023) and Smart Mobility Strategy (European Commission, 2023). However, practical Hyperloop implementation faced a lot of problems starting from installation price change and ending up with tunnelling challenges in urban, mountain or underwater areas. Hyperloop technology readiness level is on the validation of concept (Horizon, 2023) in real world trial (Walker, 2018).

From financial perspective, there are issues on how to accurately estimate costs associated with Hyperloop development especially with respect to infrastructure (Goeverden et al. 2017). Application problems revealed necessity for specific framework design, which would be a core tool for estimating. Framework purpose is to propose step-by-step roadmap for Hyperloop development implementation. It helps negotiate risks, define costs, infrastructure and technology needs for Hyperloop system installation and application.

In the first stage of the research the systematic literature review revealed knowledge gap and scientific discussion in the pneumatic train's technology. How to evaluate the impact and mitigate risks of Hyperloop implementation? How will technology change the Transport and Logistics industry? The goal of this research is to identify the theoretical foundation for discussion on Hyperloop technology implementation assessment methodology, define the relevance of the research question and limitations.

1. HYPERLOOP: HISTORICAL CONTEXT AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT

1.1. HYPERLOOP OVERVIEW

Hyperloop technology has historical background starting from the Ancient World. Instant travel was fundamental to ancient transportation thought. Ancient Greek and Roman civilizations have enabled trade and commerce, facilitated the exchange of ideas and cultures, and have been a driving force for economic growth and development. Most notable discoveries forerunning Hyperloop invention are messaging tube system, The Crystal Palace pneumatic railway in London and conceptual 'vactrain' by Robert Goddard.

"Divide a problem into small pieces", - thought Victorian Era British engineer William Murdoch. He sent a letter to a neighbour using metal pipeline by simply connecting two buildings. Further enhancing innovation by air removal from a pipe lead to a breakthrough. In fact, pneumatic transportation was invented. By that time, "cargo" was a message less than 200 grams, but proposed solution open road to new discoveries for Transport and Logistics. Posting telegrams in no-air environment became very popular due to low costs.

Hyperloop is developed by multiple vendors all over the world. Global competition is in place between various manufacturers. Lack of transparency is identified as a general problem for parties which compete for Hyperloop implementation. Parties do not share details about technology development, information is brief and provides more overview rather than insight. Technology readiness level varies from feasibility studies to testing prototypes depending on a specific vendor. Currently there is no Hyperloop technology implementation en masse.

First global hyperloop association was created to represent the hyperloop industry and provide insights to decision-makers on the hyperloop as a transportation mode. (Railwaypro, 2023).

Hardt, Hyperloop One, Hyperloop Transportation Technologies, Nevomo, TransPod, Swisspod Technologies, and Zeleros have joined forces to establish "The Hyperloop Association," the industry's first global association. The foundational document of the association was signed by the seven founding corporations on December 14, 2022.

The Brussels' based association is an important step to the growth of the hyperloop market and will support governments and institutes with hyperloop in their transportation policymaking. Further, becoming an essential factor prior to hyperloop implementation.

Analysis has been conducted to identify current manufacturers, namely stakeholders, involved in Hyperloop technology implementation. 50 different resources were scanned, and the most relevant information presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Hyperloop manufacturers. Source: companies' websites

Vendor	Location	Establishment date	Hyperloop type	Technology readiness level
China Aerospace Science and Industry Corporation (CASIC)	Beijing, China	1999	Freight	Validation of trial
EPI Center	Germany	2020	Freight	Development of alpha version
HARDT Hyperloop	Rotterdam, Netherlands	2017	Passenger	Testing
Hyperloop One	Los Angeles, California, U.S.	2017	Passenger/Cargo	Trial
HyperloopTT	Los Angeles, California, U.S.	2013	Passenger	Commercial prototype
Institute of Hyperloop Technology	Emden, Germany	2021	Passenger/Cargo	R&D
NEVOMO	Warszawa, Poland	2017	Passenger	Validation of concept
Severstal	Cherepovets, Russia	1955	Passenger/Cargo	Prototype
SpaceX	Hawthorne, California, United States	2002	Passenger/Cargo	Prototype
Swisspod	Monthey, Switzerland	2017	Passenger	Validation of concept
Transpod	Canada-France	2015	Passenger	Feasibility Study
Zeleros	Valencia, Spain	2016	Passenger	Prototype

2. HYPERLOOP ESSENCE AND CHALLENGES

2.1. COMPARISON WITH OTHER TRANSPORTATION MODES

Detailed review of pneumatic trains as fifth transportation mode defines tech travel experience more likely to be as airplane on train (Armağan, 2020). Important to mention Hyperloop was not compared to other transportation modes in this research. The review revealed problems with Hyperloop related innovations reaching the market which affects performance. Table 1 shows HL prototypes are already fast than High-speed rail with promising maximum speed by design speed overcoming both High-speed and Maglev system.

By Armağan (2020) the Hyperloop's infrastructure high level view might have similarity with the metro underground network, but connected with less stations,

Table 2: Comparison of high-speed transportation systems. Source: (Armağan, 2020).

Basic specifications of	High-speed rail	Maglev system	Hyperloop
Current maximum speed	380 km/h	431 km/h	387 km/h
Speed record	TGV (2007) 574.8 km/h	YMTL1 (2015) 603 km/h	Virgin Hyperloop One 387 km/h
Maximum design speed	402 km/h	604 km/h	1223 km/h
Maximum seating capacity	1500	824	28 per capsule
Minimum horizontal curve	7.6 km	9.1 km	4.8 km
Maximum gradient	4%	not applicable	not applicable

Hyperloop claims to be a competitive and sustainable alternative to the long-distance rail transport HSR (High Speed Rail) and the medium-distance APT (Air Passenger Transport) system (less than or equal to 1.500 km). It has been discovered that the Hyperloop system has relatively positive social/environmental performances, particularly in terms of the energy consumption, emissions of GHGs, and noise comparing with the HSR and APT system. (Goeverden et al. 2017). Hyperloop has significant value as fifth transportation mode. Technology has more energy and more velocity than any other transportation mode (Dharmeshkumar, 2021).

Figure 1: Advantages and disadvantages of Hyperloop. Source: Armağan, (2020).

To explore Hyperloop significance, it must be compared to other transportation modes. Modern diesel and electro trains can be replaced by Hyperloop. It will positively contribute to energy consumption, environment, meet modern demands and challenges (Dharmeshkumar, 2021).

Building infrastructure for Hyperloop is an expensive start (Goeverden et al. 2017). One will need to build tubes over and under the ground. Then, to ensure special environment. Implementation might be extremely costly and complicated when it comes to magnetic levitation. SpaceX team suggests air bearing suspension to replace conventional options. Technology provides stability and extremely low drag at a feasible cost (Tesla, 2022). The combination of Hyperloop, as a high-speed transportation system, and the Metaverse, a virtual reality-based environment, presents several unique advantages for both passengers and operators. Potential benefits include enhanced passenger experience, real-time information and navigation, remote collaboration, sustainable development and marketing.

East-West open trade is possible to stimulate by proper tooling. Carrying cargo through "Lisbon - Tokyo", "Los Angeles - Beijing", "Sydney-Singapore" and "London - New Delhi" routes is likely to achieve using super-fast pneumatic pods. Air transportation consumes too much fuel, damages atmosphere, and lacks security. The Hyperloop system can potentially be a very safe

mode (Goeverden et al. 2017). Fifth transportation mode leads to sustainable and secure paths amid different regions.

Hyperloop technology is still in the early stages of development and is not yet fully operational.

2.2. HYPERLOOP PERFORMANCE

Hyperloop performance against other high speed transportation systems were analysed by some authors. The competition between modern modes of transportation has remained relatively constant over the past few decades. This has not been the case for European long-distance passenger transport, where airlines have significantly increased their market share. Goeverden et.al. (2017) has estimated that air travel increased by about 45% between 2001 and 2013 while usage of the alternative modes has been rather stable (car, train) or declining (bus). Air transport increasing dominance of has enlarged the environmental impacts of long-distance transport and this trend is expected to continue in the next decades. HL is discussed as standalone mode of transport that could be a competitive and sustainable alternative to the long-distance rail transport - HSR and the medium-distance APT system.

Opgenoord et.al. (2017) proposed aerodynamic design methodology used for the aerodynamic shell. Result of the research was aerodynamic design of the MIT Hyperloop pod that allowed transportation of passengers and cargo on transonic speed. They investigated the performance of the design at transonic speed, where it was found that violating the Kantrowitz limit (Kantrowitz, 1948) could lead to three-fold increase in drag coefficient. Research proved critical importance of capsule design for Hyperloop technology implementation.

2.3. COSTS

Experiments done of the Hyperloop link from Los Angeles to San Francisco depends on four major components (Hansen, 2019):

- Capital costs for financing, land acquisition, right-of-way, construction of the infrastructure and supply of vehicles,
- Operating costs for personnel (staff, traffic control, stewards, ticketing, supervision, security, training, maintenance), energy, offices, workshops, spare parts, leasing and other equipment,
- Contracting, concessions, insurance, and
- Passengers' volume and fare revenues.

The cost of Hyperloop system construction is currently estimated to be very high (see Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of costs for Hyperloop against other transportation modes.

Transportation	Cost (Euro/km)
Hyperloop	68.8 mln*
Railway track	22.7 mln
Highway	11.2 mln
* Source: Walker, (2018)	

According to a 2017 feasibility study conducted by AECOM, the cost of building a Hyperloop system between Los Angeles and San Francisco could be as much as \$6 billion to \$7.5 billion (AECOM 2018). Additionally, the cost of operating the system would be significant, and would likely include costs such as electricity, maintenance, and staffing. The cost of building a Hyperloop system would also depend on factors such as the distance of the route, the number of stops, and the type of terrain.

Infrastructure construction costs depend in the first instance on the number of tubes, the total length of the Hyperloop line, the number of stations and platforms, as well as on the length of elevated and underground sections, the level above/below the ground or sea, respectively, geological characteristics of the subsurface, and finally the civil construction costs for the pylons, tunnels, and tubes. Solution, purpose, and technology availability should be considered during the final price calculation.

2.4. TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

Some of the main technical feasibility challenges include:

Propulsion: Achieving the high speeds needed for Hyperloop requires a powerful and efficient propulsion system.

Vacuum tube: To minimize air resistance and increase speed, Hyperloop systems would need to operate in a vacuum tube.

Guidance: Hyperloop pods would need to be guided along the track with a high degree of precision in order to maintain stability and safety.

Temperature and pressure control: Maintaining a vacuum within the tube would require the development of a system that can control the temperature and pressure within the tube.

Safety: Hyperloop systems would need to be designed with safety in mind, and would need to meet strict safety standards.

Control and communication: Hyperloop systems would require advanced control and communication systems to ensure the safe operation of the pods, and the coordination of multiple pods travelling at high speeds.

Scalability: Hyperloop systems would need to be designed to be scalable, as the technology is still in development.

2.5. SAFETY

Hyperloop safety challenges include:

Emergency systems: Hyperloop systems would need to have adequate emergency systems in place to ensure the safety of passengers and cargo in the event of an incident.

Fire safety: Fire safety is a significant concern in a vacuum tube environment, where there is limited air flow. The Hyperloop system would need to be designed to prevent fires, and have systems in place to detect and extinguish fires quickly if they do occur.

Crashworthiness: Hyperloop pods would need to be designed to be crashworthy, in order to protect passengers and cargo in the event of an accident. This would include designing the pods to be able to withstand impact and providing adequate protection for the passengers and cargo inside the pod.

Risk assessment: Hyperloop systems would need to be designed with risk assessment in mind, in order to identify and mitigate potential safety risks.

Cybersecurity: Hyperloop systems would rely heavily on technology and automation, which would make it critical to ensure that the system is secure against cyber-attacks.

Maintenance and inspection: Hyperloop systems would require regular maintenance and inspection to ensure that they are safe and reliable.

Emergency response plan: Hyperloop systems would require an emergency response plan to deal with potential incidents.

2.6. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Environmental impact is of high importance for HL technology as it crosses both urban and rural areas, including over- and under- ground, and over- and under- water. Some of the main environmental impact challenges for Hyperloop include:

Energy consumption: HL infrastructure requires a significant amount of energy to operate. System is necessary in place to power the pods and maintain the vacuum within the tube.

Land use: The construction of Hyperloop systems would require a significant amount of land, and there would need to be an assessment of the impact on wildlife and natural habitats.

Noise pollution: Hyperloop systems would generate noise, which could have an impact on the environment.

Emissions: Hyperloop systems would need to be designed to minimize emissions, and would need to comply with emissions standards.

Sustainability: system design should correlate with sustainability, and would need to be made from materials that are environmentally friendly.

Life cycle assessment: Hyperloop systems would need to undergo a life cycle assessment to evaluate their environmental impact, from the extraction of raw materials to the end of their service life.

Public acceptance: As with any new mode of transportation, it is important to gain public acceptance. This includes educating the public on the environmental impact concerns.

2.7. PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE

Hyperloop technology is still a new concept, and there are several challenges that must be overcome in order to gain public acceptance of the technology. Some of the main public acceptance challenges for Hyperloop include:

Public education: In order to gain public acceptance, it is important to educate the public on the benefits and safety of Hyperloop technology.

Addressing concerns: The public may have concerns about Hyperloop technology, such as safety, environmental impact, and cost.

Building trust: Gaining public acceptance also means building trust with the public. This could include involving the public in the development process, and providing information about the testing and safety measures that are in place.

Overcoming stereotypes: Hyperloop technology is still new, and there may be stereotypes associated with it, such as being a technology that is only available to the rich.

Transparency: Being transparent in the development process and decision making can help to build trust with the public, and provide them with the information they need to make informed decisions about the technology.

Public engagement: Engaging with the public and involving them in the development process can help to build support for the technology and address concerns early on.

Communication: Effective communication is key to gaining public acceptance

2.8. REGULATORY AND LEGAL ISSUES

European Joint Research Centre study examined the status of Hyperloop development and identified issues and challenges by means of a systematic review on Hyperloop since 2014 (Gkoumas, 2021). Recently, HL was included in the trans-European transport network (TEN-T) rules to make sure technology is in line with European mobility objectives of sustainability, safety, network resilience, and seamless connections of people and goods (European Parliament, 2023). However, HL implementation faced regulatory issues all over the world and it's subject of regional politics and policy.

Some of the main regulatory and legal issues for Hyperloop include:

Regulations: Lack of regulations in place to govern the operation of Hyperloop systems.

Certification: Hyperloop systems would need to be certified before they can be operated commercially.

Liability: lack of transparency how liability would be handled in the event of an incident.

Insurance: Hyperloop systems would need to be insured before they can be operated commercially.

Intellectual property: a potential for disputes over intellectual property rights is present.

Permits and licenses: necessity to obtain permits and licenses before they can be operated commercially.

2.9. HYPERLOOP FOR CARGO

Hyperloop technology has the potential to be used for the transportation of freight as well as passengers. The high speeds and low friction of the system would allow for fast and efficient transportation of goods. Additionally, the use of Hyperloop for freight could reduce the number of trucks on highways, which would have a positive impact on traffic congestion and air pollution. Some companies are currently working on developing Hyperloop technology specifically for freight transportation. For example, Virgin Hyperloop has announced plans to develop a "Hyperloop for cargo" system that would use the same technology as its passenger system to transport freight.

3. HYPERLOOP MODALITY

3.1. HYPERLOOP AS UNIMODAL TRANSPORTATION MODE

Original Hyperloop Alpha Paper created by the Elon Musk (Tesla, 2023) proposes technology as the solution for the specific case of high traffic city pairs that are less than about 1500 km or 900 miles apart. Tesla case proposes to connect city pairs, namely from point “A” to “B” with a bullet-speed train. There are no stops planned between these points, meaning it is nearly impossible to stop a Hyperloop in case of emergency and would require special framework to meet these requirements.

SpaceX Hyperloop case is unimodal, distance route from “A” to “B” is not used by other transportation modes and Hyperloop technology itself is not part of any other transportation system. Tesla elaborates on a use-case where Hyperloop is fifth transportation mode. It fits main transportation unimodality features and requirements.

3.2. HYPERLOOP AS MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATION MODE

Hyperloop technology has the potential to be integrated as a multimodal transportation mode, meaning it could be connected with other forms of transportation such as trains, buses, and cars. This would allow for a more efficient and seamless transportation system, providing more options for passengers to reach their destinations. Some of the benefits of integrating Hyperloop as a multimodal transportation mode include:

Increased connectivity: Integrating Hyperloop with other forms of transportation would increase connectivity between different regions and cities. This would allow for more efficient travel, and make it easier for people to reach their destinations.

Reduced travel time: Integrating Hyperloop with other forms of transportation would allow for even faster travel, making it a more attractive option for passengers.

Increased capacity: increase the overall capacity of the transportation system.

Cost-effective: reduce the need for expensive infrastructure such as highways and airports.

Increased sustainability: reduce the need for cars and airplanes, which are major sources of greenhouse gas emissions.

Flexibility: Integrating Hyperloop with other forms of transportation would provide more flexibility for passengers, as they would have more options for how to reach their destinations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The presented Literature Review helped to collect and research the state of current knowledge in Hyperloop technology. It helped to understand in depth the research problem and establish the theoretical framework of the research. Systematic view of Hyperloop implementation challenges is designed (Figure 2).

Study defined a knowledge gap in the Hyperloop technology implementation field. There is no unified step-by-step methodology dedicated to Hyperloop implementation to assess the impact and risks. Current technology readiness level is on the concept validation in trial. Scientific community is separated into different camps on Hyperloop implementation. Some research criticise technology as science fiction not relevant for current demand of transportation system, being too expensive and lacking proper background for implementation. Debates on technology make positive impact on innovations in transportation industry.

HL solutions are not systemised, there is no agreement on technology design and implementation, system design is not stable. Costs estimation for HL construction lack structured approach. Implementation process and price estimation lacks transparency. Current HL risk assessment lacks proper indexes and only discussion is present based on concrete implementation. Technology impact is investigated only on general level, however, could not be applied to technology itself due to recent developments. Current HL developments missing success factors for implementation due to low technology readiness level.

Hyperloop technology is considered important for several reasons:

Speed: With speeds of up to 1200 km/h, Hyperloop would be one of the fastest forms of transportation in the world.

Capacity: Ability to transport passengers and cargo at ultra-high speeds would increase the overall capacity of the transportation system, making it a more.

Sustainability: Hyperloop systems would be powered by electricity, and would generate far less greenhouse gas emissions than traditional forms of transportation.

Cost-effective: Hyperloop technology has the potential to be more cost-effective than other forms of transportation, such as highways and airports.

Safety: Hyperloop technology is designed to be a safe form of transportation, and would be equipped with state-of-the-art safety systems to ensure the safety of passengers and cargo.

Connectivity: Hyperloop technology would increase connectivity between different regions and cities, making it easier for people to travel between destinations.

Main Hyperloop technology challenges include:

Technical feasibility: Hyperloop technology is still in the early stages of development, and there are several technical challenges that must be overcome in order to make the technology viable.

Costs: Building and operating a Hyperloop system would be very expensive with potential significant deviation between estimated and final technology costs.

Safety: Hyperloop systems would need to be designed with safety in mind, and would need to meet strict safety standards.

Environmental Impact: Hyperloop systems would likely have an impact on the environment, and would need to be designed with sustainability in mind. There would need to be an assessment of the environmental impact of the system.

Regulatory and legal issues: Hyperloop technology is still a new concept, and there is currently lack of regulations in place to govern the operation of Hyperloop systems..

Public acceptance: As with any new mode of transportation, it is important to gain public acceptance. This includes educating the public on the benefits and safety of the technology, and addressing any concerns they may have.

Modality: HL technology can be unimodal or multimodal depending on case and scenario of implementation. Depending on the modality HL system changes and different technology implementation is needed.

To summarize:

1. Knowledge gap is present in Hyperloop technology implementation.
2. Hyperloop technology readiness level is on validation of concept in trial. There is no finalised HL implementation en-masse.
3. Hyperloop solutions are not systemised.
4. Hyperloop implementation and cost estimation process is not transparent.
5. Technology impact is not assessed in structured way.
6. System design is not stable.
7. System purpose is not defined.
8. Hyperloop community lacks structured approach on technology implementation.
9. There is not tool for HL-related costs and impact calculation.
10. Hyperloop technology practical implementations is slowed down due lack of proper regulatory and legal frameworks.

Further research is needed to design assessment methodology how to assess the impact, mitigate risks and develop criteria for successful Hyperloop technology implementation.

Figure 2. Systematic view of Hyperloop implementation challenges. Hard line represents connections between categorized challenges and corresponding subcategories. Dotted line represents interconnectivity between Hyperloop implementation challenges.

REFERENCES

- AECOM (2018). *THE FUTURE OF INFRASTRUCTURE*. Available: https://infrastructure.aecom.com/hubfs/report/FOI_Report_US.pdf?utm
- K. Armağan (2020) The fifth mode of transportation: Hyperloop. *Journal of Innovative Transportation, Turkey*. Available: <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/jit/issue/55759/761535>
- C. A. Dharmeshkumar (2021). Hyperloop: V Mode of Transportation. *IJERT*, ISSN: 2278-0181. Available: <https://www.ijert.org/hyperloop-v-mode-of-transportation>
- J. Doppelbauer (2022), Hyperloop – an Innovation for Global Transportation? Available: https://www.era.europa.eu/sites/default/files/library/docs/hyperloop_innovation_for_global_transportation_en_1.pdf
- European Commission (2023). Available: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/mobility-strategy_en
- European Parliament (2023). Available: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20230411IPR79503/trans-european-transport-projects-first-go-ahead-to-new-rules>
- European Union Agency for Railways (2023), ERA. Available: https://www.era.europa.eu/sites/default/files/library/docs/hyperloop_innovation_for_global_transportation_en_1.pdf
- EPICenter (2023) European Hyperloop Technology. Available: <https://epicenterproject.eu/news-events/european-hyperloop-technology>
- K. Gkoumas (2021) Hyperloop Academic Research: A Systematic Review and a Taxonomy of Issues. *Ispira, Italy*. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/app11135951>
- GIH (2022) Global Infrastructure Hub, Hyperloop for High-Speed Passenger Transport. Available: <https://cdn.gihub.org/umbraco/media/3201/2-hyperloop-use-case.pdf>
- K. V. Goeverden, D. Milakis, R Konings (2017). Performances of the Hyperloop (HL) transport system. *BIVEC-GIBET Transport Research Days 2017, Liège, Belgium*. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-018-0312-x>
- I.Hansen (2019). Hyperloop transport technology assessment and system analysis. *Transportation Planning and Technology*. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03081060.2020.1828935>
- G.Hollister-Short, F.James (1992). *History of Technology Volume 17*. Bloomsbury: pp.165-167.

Horizon (2023). Hyperloop Industrial Roadmap and pilots. Available: <https://www.horizon-europe.gouv.fr/hyperloop-industrial-roadmap-and-pilots-31237>

Hyperloop One (2023). Available: <https://www.hyperloop-one.com>

M.Jost (2015). *Hermes*. Oxford University Press 2023. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199381135.013.3038>

Kantrowitz, M. (1948). Theoretical Rocket Performance at High Altitudes. *Journal of the Aeronautical Sciences*, 15(10), 613-619.

J.K. Nøland (2021), Prospects and Challenges of the Hyperloop Transportation System: A Systematic Technology Review. *Norwegian University of Science and Technology*. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=9350309>

M.Opgenoord, P.Caplan (2017), On the Aerodynamic Design of the Hyperloop Concept. 35th AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318012905_On_the_Aerodynamic_Design_of_the_Hyperloop_Concept

Railbaltica (2023), Rail Baltica Global Project. Available: <https://www.railbaltica.org>

Railwaypro (2023), First international Hyperloop Association created. Available: <https://www.railwaypro.com/wp/first-international-hyperloop-association-created/>

A. Rossolov, D. Kopytkov, Y. Kush, V. Zadorozhna (2017). RESEARCH OF EFFECTIVENESS OF UNIMODAL AND MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATION INVOLVING LAND MODES OF TRANSPORT. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies ISSN 1729-3774*. Kharkiv, Ukraine. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2017.112356>

Tesla (2023). Available: https://www.tesla.com/sites/default/files/blog_images/hyperloop-alpha.pdf

R. Walker (2018). Hyperloop: Cutting through the hype. Available: <https://trl.co.uk/uploads/trl/documents/ACA003-Hyperloop.pdf>